

Figure S1. Local phylogenetic signal hotspots for X1~X10 traits.

Figure S2. Local phylogenetic signal hotspots for X11~X20 traits.

Figure S3. Local phylogenetic signal hotspots for X21~X30 traits.

Figure S4. Local phylogenetic signal hotspots for X31~X40 traits.

Figure S5. Local phylogenetic signal hotspots for X41~X50 traits.

Figure S6. Local phylogenetic signal hotspots for X51~X60 traits.

Figure S7. Local phylogenetic signal hotspots for X61~X70 traits.

Figure S8. Local phylogenetic signal hotspots for X71~X80 traits.

Figure S9. Local phylogenetic signal hotspots for X81~X90 traits.

Figure S10. Local phylogenetic signal hotspots for X91~X100 traits.

Figure S11. Local phylogenetic signal hotspots for X101~X110 traits.

Figure S12. Local phylogenetic signal hotspots for X111~X120 traits.

Figure S13. Local phylogenetic signal hotspots for X121~X130 traits.

Figure S14. Local phylogenetic signal hotspots for X131~X142 traits.

Figure S15. UCE extraction rate.

Figure S16. Phylogenetic tree based on UCE.